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EVALUATION OF QUALITY PARAMETERS OF THREE DIFFERENT MARKETED BRANDS OF AROGYAVARDHINI VATI: A HERBO-MINERAL FORMULATION

Princy Agarwal*, Rajat Vaishnav, Anju Goyal

Department of Quality Assurance, Bhupal Nobles Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Sevashram Road, Udaipur-313002, Rajasthan, India.

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ABSTRACT

Arogyavardhini vati is a herbo-mineral formulation which is one of the most commonly used preparation in Ayurvedic clinical practice since ages. Objective: The present work was carried out with the view to comparatively evaluate three different and popular marketed formulations of Arogyavardhini Vati in order to confirm its quality and also to highlight the variations that may be present in them so that recommendations can be proposed regarding the quality and consistency of marketed formulations. Methods: Three different and popular marketed formulations of Arogyavardhini Vati were assessed comparatively for their organoleptic, physicochemical and phytochemical properties as per the methods prescribed in Pharmacopoeias. Results: The analysis of the data revealed that all the parameters of three brands of Arogyavardhini Vati had approximately similar values having difference in the values of Alcohol soluble extractives of Brand B and of Water soluble extractives of Brand A both having values comparatively lesser than the other two brands. There was also a considerable difference in the values of Hardness and Disintegration time of Brand B respectively. Conclusion: The data originated from the present study will be very useful for routine quality control and also to control the batch to batch variation among the formulations.

Corresponding author

Princy Agarwal

Department of Quality Assurance,
Bhupal Nobles Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Sevashram Road, Udaipur-313002, Rajasthan, India.
princyagarwal2992@gmail.com
9772640100.

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INTRODUCTION

Traditional herbal medicine and its preparations have been widely used for thousands of years in developing and developed countries due to its natural origin and side effects or dissatisfaction with the results of synthetic drugs. Most of the traditional medical system are effective, but only one of the main disadvantages is the lack of standardization. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a standardization technique to develop this system of medicine to the extent of the modern world and to mix it with the mainstream of the health sciences. [1] The World Health Organization also stressed the need to ensure the quality of medicinal plant products through the use of modern control techniques and the application of appropriate standards. [2]

Arogyavardhini vati is one of the formulations of herbo-minerals explained in Rasa Ratna Samuchchaya. [3] The word "Arogya" means good health and "Vardhini" means enhancer. It means, a formulation that improves good health is known as "Arogyavardhini". This is used in the imbalances of the three Doshas (humor). This formulation is well known for its properties of Deepana-Pachana (enhancer of digestion and metabolism). It is used for leprosy, fever, edema, obesity, jaundice and other liver disorders. Medicine is also good for lack of appetite, indigestion and irregular bowels, liver disorders and skin diseases. It acts as an alternative to carminative and stomachic. [4]

The present work was carried out to standardize and evaluate the pharmaceutical, physicochemical and pharmacognostical properties of three different marketed brands of Arogyavardhini Vati.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: [5-13]

PROCUREMENT OF SAMPLES:

The following marketed Arogyavardhini Vati preparations were used in the present study. Brand A (Batch No. SB 0159), Brand B (Batch No. G-1601), Brand C (Batch No. #B-AVV041). All brands of the Arogyavardhini Vati were procured from the local market from the registered Ayurvedic Pharmacy.

ORGANOLEPTIC EVALUATION:

All the organoleptic properties viz. color and odor of the drug were performed as per standard procedure and noted down.

PHARMACEUTICAL EVALUATION:

Pharmaceutical parameters like Weight variation, Thickness, Diameter, Hardness, Friability and Disintegration time were determined as per standard protocols.

Determination of Weight Variation

20 tablets were weighed at random and the average weight of the tablets was calculated. Then the individual weight of the tablet was compared with the average weight.

Acceptance criteria: Not more than 2 individual tablet weights deviate from the average weight by more than the deviation stated in the Pharmacopoeia.

Table 1: Weight Variation Limits as per Various Pharmacopoeias.

IP/BP	LIMIT	USP
80 mg or less	± 10%	130 mg or less
80 – 250 mg	± 7.5%	130 – 324 mg
>250 mg	± 5%	>324 mg

Determination of Thickness and Diameter

The crown tablet thickness and diameter of an individual tablet was measured with a Digital Vernier caliper, which permits accurate measurements and provides information on the variation between the tablets.

Determination of Hardness

Hardness of a tablet can be measured by using Monsanto or Pfizer tablet hardness testers. We have made the use of Monsanto hardness tester.

Determination of Friability

The tablets were carefully de-dusted prior to testing. Then accurately weighed tablet sample (as per standards described in Pharmacopoeias) was placed in the drum. The drum was rotated 100 times, and the tablets were removed. The tablets were again de-dusted and accurately weighed.

Acceptance criteria: A maximum mean weight loss from the three samples of not more than 1.0% is considered acceptable for most products.

Formula for calculation:

$$\text{Friability} = \frac{I_w - F_w}{I_w} \times 100 \%$$

Where,

I_w = Initial weight of tablets

F_w = Final weight of tablets

Determination of Disintegration Time

For the disintegration test one tablet was placed in each tube, the guided disc was placed above each tablet and the basket rack was positioned in 1 L beaker containing water at $37 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. For compliance with USP standards the tablets must disintegrate and all particles must pass through the 10 mesh screen in the specified time. If any residue remains it must have a soft mass with no palpably firm core. In the case of Ayurvedic tablets the disintegration time required for five tablets should not be more than 15 minutes, unless otherwise stated in the monograph.

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL EVALUATION:

Physicochemical parameters like moisture content (Loss on Drying), pH, total ash, acid Insoluble ash, water-soluble extractive, alcohol soluble extractive values of all three samples were determined as per standard protocols. All the procedures are described as follows:

Determination of Moisture Content/ Loss on Drying (LOD)

An accurately weighed 5g of polyherbal formulation powder was taken in a tarred evaporating dish. The crude drug was then heated at 105°C in an oven for 3 hours. The drying and weighing was continued at half an hour interval until difference between two successive weighing corresponded to, not more than 0.25 per cent. Percentage moisture content of the sample was calculated with reference to the air dried powdered drug material.

Formula for calculation:

$$\% \text{ LOD} = \frac{W_2 - W_3}{W_3 - W_1} \times 100 \%$$

Where,

W_1 = weight of container (g)

W_2 = weight of container + wet sample (g)

W_3 = weight of container + dried sample (g)

$W_2 - W_3$ = weight of moisture

$W_3 - W_1$ = weight of dried sample

Determination of Loss on Ignition (LOI):

An accurately weighed 5g of polyherbal formulation powder was taken in a previously ignited and tared silica crucible and was heated in the oven at 105°C overnight (or the previously dried sample can also be used). The crucible was cooled and reweighed. The crucible was then placed into the furnace tray and was ignited in the Muffle Furnace at 500°C for about 4 hrs. The sample was then cooled in a dessicator for 30 min. and reweighed with the ash in it (W_A). The observations were noted.

Formula for calculation:

$$\% \text{ LOI} = \frac{W_S - W_A}{W_S - W_C} \times 100 \%$$

Where,

W_C = weight of crucible (g)

W_S = weight of sample (g)

W_A = weight of ash (g)

Determination of Total Ash

An accurately weighed 3 g of the sample was taken in a previously ignited and tared silica dish/crucible. The material was evenly spread and ignited in a Muffle Furnace by gradually increasing the temperature to not more than 450°C - 600°C till the carbon free ash was not obtained. The Total Ash value was calculated with reference to the air-dried powdered drug material.

Formula for calculation:

$$\% \text{ Total Ash} = \frac{\text{Weight of Ash}}{\text{Weight of sample taken}} \times 100 \%$$

Determination of Acid Insoluble Ash

Ash above obtained, was boiled for 5 min with 25ml of 1M Hydrochloric acid and filtered using an ash less filter paper. Insoluble matter retained on filter paper was washed with hot water and filter paper was burnt to a constant weight in a muffle furnace. The percentage of acid insoluble ash was calculated with reference to the air-dried powdered drug material.

Formula for calculation:

$$\% \text{ Acid - Insoluble Ash} = \frac{\text{Weight of acid insoluble residue}}{\text{Weight of sample taken}} \times 100 \%$$

Determination of Water Soluble Ash:

1g of ash obtained in total ash experiment was boiled for 5 min with 25ml water and insoluble matter collected on an ashless filter paper which was then washed with hot water and ignited for 15 min at a temperature not exceeding 450°C in a muffle furnace. Difference in weight of ash and weight of insoluble matter was determined as difference represents the value. The percentage of water insoluble ash was calculated with reference to the air-dried powdered drug material.

Formula for calculation:

$$\% \text{ Water Soluble Ash} = \frac{\text{Weight of water soluble residue}}{\text{Weight of sample taken}} \times 100 \%$$

Determination of Extractive Values**a. Determination of Alcohol Soluble Extractives:**

5 gm of churna was accurately weighed and placed inside a glass stoppered conical flask. It was then macerated with 100ml of ethanol. The flask was shaken frequently during the first 6 hours and was kept aside without disturbing for 18 hours. It was then filtered and about 25ml of filtrate was transferred into a tared flat-bottomed shallow dish and was evaporated to dryness on a water bath. It was then dried to 105° C for 6 hours, cooled and finally weighed. The percentage of Alcohol Soluble extractives was calculated with reference to the air-dried powdered drug material.

Formula for calculation:

$$\% \text{ Alcohol Soluble Extractive} = \frac{\text{Weight of residue} \times 100 \times 100}{25 \times \text{Weight of sample taken}} \%$$

b. Determination of Water Soluble Extractives:

Proceed as directed for determination of Alcohol-Soluble Extractive, using *chloroform water* (2.5 ml chloroform in purified water to produce 1000 ml) instead of *ethanol*.

Determination of pH Value

The powder sample of Arogyavardhini Vati was weighed to about 5g and immersed in 100 ml of water in a beaker. The beaker was closed with aluminum foil and left behind for 24 hours in room temperature. Later the supernatant solution was decanted into another beaker and the pH of the formulation was determined using a calibrated digital pH meter.

PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION:

The aqueous and alcoholic extracts of the respective formulations were prepared and were subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening. These tests reveal the presence of various bioactive secondary metabolites which might be responsible for their medicinal attributes. Methods for preliminary qualitative phytochemical tests of the plant extracts are given below in the Table 2.

Table 2: Preliminary Phytochemical Tests for Plant Extracts.

S.No.	Phyto-Constituents	Name of Tests	Procedure	Observation
1.	Alkaloids	Mayer's test	2 ml extract + few drops of HCl + Mayer's reagent	Cream Precipitation
		Hager's test	2 ml extract + few drops of HCl + Hager's reagent	Yellow Precipitation
		Wagner's test	2 ml extract + few drops of HCl + Wagner's reagent	Reddish brown color
2.	Carbohydrates	Molish test	2 ml extract + 2 Drops of Molish reagent + few drops of Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Violet or Reddish color
3.	Reducing sugars	Fehling's test	1 ml extract + 1 ml Fehling Solution	First Yellow then Brick Red Precipitation
4.	Flavonoids	Alkaline reagent test	2 ml extract + few drops of 40% NaOH solution	Intense yellow color forms which becomes colorless on addition of dil. acid
		Lead acetate test	2 ml extract + few drops of Lead Acetate solution	Yellow precipitation
5.	Saponins	Foam test	2 ml extract + 4 ml distilled H ₂ O Mix well and shake vigorously	Foam formation
6.	Tannins	Braymer's test	2 ml extract + 2 ml H ₂ O + 2-3 drops of 5% FeCl ₃	Black green or bluish color
7.	Steroids	Salkowski's test	2 ml extract + 2 ml Chloroform + 2 ml Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Chloroform layer appears red and acid layer shows greenish-yellow fluorescence
8.	Proteins	Millon's test	3 ml extract + 5 ml Millon's reagent	White precipitate which turns brick red on warming

9.	Glycosides	Keller Killiani's test	2 ml extract + Glacial acetic Acid + 1 drop of 5% FeCl ₃ + Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Reddish brown color appears at the junction of 2 layers and upper layer appears bluish green
10.	Phenols	-	2-3 ml of extract + few drops of 5% FeCl ₃ solution 2-3 ml of extract + few drops of Lead Acetate solution	Deep blue-black color White precipitate
11.	Amino acids	Ninhydrin test	3 ml of extract + 3 drops of 5% Ninhydrin solution Keep in boiling water bath for 10 min.	Purple or bluish color appears
12.	Terpenoids	Copper Acetate test	2 ml extract dissolved in water + 3-4 drops of Copper Acetate solution	Emerald green color

DETERMINATION OF HEAVY METALS (LEAD AND CADMIUM)

Method (Direct Calibration Method)

Three reference solutions of the element being examined having different concentrations were prepared covering the range recommended by the instrument manufacturer. Separately the corresponding reagents were added for the test solution and the blank solution was prepared with the corresponding reagents. The absorbance of the blank solution and each reference solution were measured separately, and the readings were recorded. A calibration curve was prepared with the average value of 3 readings of each concentration on the ordinate and the corresponding concentration on the abscissa. A test solution of the substance being examined was prepared as specified in the monograph. The concentration was adjusted such that it falls within the concentration range of the reference solution. The absorbance was measured 3 times, and the readings were recorded and the average value was calculated. The mean value was interpolated on the calibration curve to determine the concentration of the element.

Preparation of Lead standard solution:

Lead standard solutions were prepared from Stock solution (1000 ppm Sisco Research Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. stock solution). Standard solutions of concentrations, 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 ppm were prepared. The absorption of standard solution measured at 217 nm using hollow cathode lamp as a light source & air acetylene blue flame on Atomic absorption Spectrophotometer.

Preparation of Cadmium standard solution:

Cadmium standard solutions were prepared from Stock solution (1000 ppm Sisco Research Laboratories Pvt. Ltd. stock solution). Standard solutions of concentrations 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8 and 1.0 ppm was prepared. The absorption of standard solution measured at 228.8 nm using hollow cathode lamp as a light source & air acetylene blue flame on Atomic absorption Spectrophotometer.

Preparation of Test solution:

Weigh accurately about 0.5 g of the coarse powder of the substance being examined, transfer into a casparian flask, add 5-10 ml of the mixture of nitric acid (HNO₃) and perchloric acid (HClO₄) (4 : 1), add a small hopper on the flask-top, macerate overnight, heat to slake on the electric hot plate, keep somewhat-boiling, if brownish-black in color, add again a quantity of the above mixture, continuously heat till the solution becomes clear and transparent, then raise temperature, heat continuously to thick smoke, till white smoke disperse, the slaked solution becomes colorless and transparent or a little yellow, cool, transfer it into a 50 ml volumetric flask, wash the container with 2% nitric acid solution (HNO₃), add the washing solution into the same volumetric flask and dilute with the same solvent to the volume, shake well. Prepare synchronously the reagent blank solution according to the above procedure.

Determination:

Measure accurately 1 ml of the test solution and its corresponding reagent blank solution respectively, add 1 ml of solution containing 1% NH₄H₂PO₄ and 0.2% Mg(NO₃)₂, shake well, pipette accurately 10-20 µl to determine the absorbance.

Sample analysis:

The analysis of the digested samples were carried out using an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (EC Electronics Corporation of India limited AAS Element AS AAS4141) for Lead and Cadmium. The instrumental conditions for Lead analysis are depicted in Table 3.

TABLE 3: Instrumental Conditions for Analysis of Lead and Cadmium.

Parameters	Pb	Cd
Wavelength (nm)	217	228.8
Slit width (nm)	1.0	0.5
Light Source	Hollow Cathode Lamp	Hollow Cathode Lamp
Flame type	Air/C ₂ H ₂	Air/C ₂ H ₂
Current	10	3.5
AAS Technique	Flame	Flame

RESULTS:**ORGANOLEPTIC EVALUATION**

The observations for the organoleptic evaluation of three brands of Arogyavardhini Vati are reported in Table-4.

Table 4: Results for Organoleptic Evaluation of different brands of Arogyavardhini Vati.

S.No.	PROPERTIES	BRAND A	BRAND B	BRAND C
1.	Description	Solid Tablets	Solid Tablets	Solid Tablets
2.	Color	Dark Brown	Dark Brown	Blackish Brown
3.	Odor	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic

PHARMACEUTICAL EVALUATION

The observations for the pharmaceutical evaluation of three brands of Arogyavardhini Vati are reported in Table-5.

Table 5: Results for Pharmaceutical Evaluation of different brands of Arogyavardhini Vati.

S.No.	PROPERTIES	BRAND A	BRAND B	BRAND C
1.	Weight Variation	Passed	Passed	Passed
2.	Thickness	3.98±0.021	4.64±0.26	4.39±0.42
3.	Diameter	9.73±0.026	9.85±0.01	9.24±0.012
4.	Hardness	8.17±0.289	4.33±0.763	11.17±0.289
5.	Friability	0.51%	0.38%	0.07%
6.	Disintegration Time	57 min.	65 min	55 min

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL EVALUATION

The observations for the physico-chemical evaluation of three brands of Arogyavardhini Vati are reported in Table-6.

Table 6: Results for Physico-chemical Evaluation of different brands of Arogyavardhini Vati.

S.No.	PROPERTIES	BRAND A	BRAND B	BRAND C
1.	pH	4.6	4.7	4.9
2.	Loss on Drying/ Moisture Content	6.39%	8.0%	6.84%
3.	Water Soluble Extractive	24.0%	39.2%	42.4%
4.	Alcohol Soluble Extractive	8.0%	3.2%	5.6%
5.	Loss on Ignition	1.03%	4.01%	3.48%
6.	Total Ash Value	18.68%	16.88%	17.44%
7.	Acid Insoluble Ash	1.31%	2.72%	1.17%
8.	Water Soluble Ash	9.77%	10.07%	9.92%

PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION

The observations for the phytochemical evaluation of three brands of Arogyavardhini Vati are reported in Table-7.

Table 7: Phytochemical Screening of Arogyavardhini Vati.

S. No.	PHYTO-CONSTITUENT	NAME OF TESTS	BRAND A		BRAND B		BRAND C	
			Aq.	Alco.	Aq.	Alco.	Aq.	Alco.
1.	Alkaloids	Hager's test	-	+	-	+	-	+
		Wagner's test	-	+	-	+	-	+
		Mayer's test	-	+	-	+	-	+
2.	Glycosides	Keller Killani's test	+	+	+	+	+	+
		Molish's test	+	+	+	+	+	+
4.	Proteins	Biuret's test	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Millon's test	-	-	-	-	-	-
5.	Amino Acids	Ninhydrin's test	-	-	-	-	-	-
6.	Steroids	Salkowski's test	+	+	+	+	+	+
7.	Flavonoids	Alkaline Reagent test	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Lead acetate test	-	-	-	-	-	-
8.	Terpenoids	Copper Acetate test	+	+	+	+	+	+
9.	Tannins	Ferric Chloride test	+	+	+	+	+	+
10.	Saponins	Foam test	-	-	-	-	-	-
11.	Phenols	Ferric Chloride test	-	-	-	-	-	-
		Lead Acetate test	-	-	-	-	-	-

DETERMINATION OF HEAVY METALS (LEAD AND CADMIUM)

The observations for the heavy metal determination of three brands of Arogyavardhini Vati are reported in Table-8.

Table 8: Heavy metal analysis of Arogyavardhini Vati.

S.No.	PROPERTIES	BRAND A	BRAND B	BRAND C	STANDARD (API)
18.	Heavy Metal Concentration (ppm)				
a.	Lead	1.505	2.923	2.506	10 ppm
b.	Cadmium	0.125	0.167	0.098	0.3 ppm

Graph 1: Graphs for various Pharmaceutical and Physico-chemical parameters of different brands of Arogyavardhini Vati.

DISCUSSION

Arogyavardhini vati of *Brand A* was of solid state of Dark brown color. This preparation had pH value of 4.6, and Loss on drying value of 6.39% w/w. Preparation had Alcohol soluble extractives and Water soluble extractives values of 8.0% w/w and 24.0% w/w respectively. The tablets passed the Weight variation test as per IP standards. The mean value and standard deviation of Thickness and Diameter of the tablets were 3.98 ± 0.021 and 9.73 ± 0.026 respectively. The tablet had Hardness value of 8.17 ± 0.289 . The Friability and Disintegration time of the tablets were 0.51% and 57 min. respectively. It had Total Ash value of 18.68% w/w, and Acid insoluble ash and Water soluble ash value of 1.31% w/w and 9.77% w/w respectively. Loss on ignition was found 1.03% w/w.

The concentrations for heavy metals Lead and Cadmium were found to be 1.505 and 0.125 respectively which were within the prescribed limits. Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of Glycosides, Carbohydrates, Steroids, Tannins and Terpenoids in both the extracts and of Alkaloids in alcoholic extract only.

Arogyavardhini vati of *Brand B* was of solid state of Dark brown color. This preparation had pH value of 4.7, and Loss on drying value of 8.0% w/w. Preparation had Alcohol soluble extractives and Water soluble extractives values of 3.2% w/w and 39.2% w/w respectively. The tablets passed the Weight variation test as per IP standards. The mean value and standard deviation of Thickness and Diameter of the tablets were 4.64 ± 0.26 and 9.85 ± 0.01 respectively. The tablet had Hardness value of 4.33 ± 0.763 . The Friability and Disintegration time of the tablets were 0.38% and 65 min. respectively. It had Total Ash value of 16.88% w/w, and Acid insoluble ash and Water soluble ash value of 2.72% w/w and 10.07% w/w respectively. Loss on ignition was found 4.01% w/w. The concentrations for heavy metals Lead and Cadmium were found to be 2.923 and 0.167 respectively which were within the prescribed limits. Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of Glycosides, Carbohydrates, Steroids, Tannins and Terpenoids in both the extracts and of Alkaloids in alcoholic extract only.

Arogyavardhini vati of *Brand C* was of solid state of Blackish brown color. This preparation had pH value of 4.9, and Loss on drying value of 6.84% w/w. Preparation had Alcohol soluble extractives and Water soluble extractives values of 5.6% w/w and 42.4% w/w respectively. The tablets passed the Weight variation test as per IP standards. The mean value and standard deviation of Thickness and Diameter of the tablets were 4.39 ± 0.42 and 9.24 ± 0.012 respectively. The tablet had Hardness value of 11.17 ± 0.289 . The Friability and Disintegration time of the tablets were 0.07% and 55 min. respectively. It had Total Ash value of 17.44% w/w, and Acid insoluble ash and Water soluble ash value of 1.17% w/w and 9.92% w/w respectively. Loss on ignition was found 3.48% w/w. The concentrations for heavy metals Lead and Cadmium were found to be 2.506 and 0.098 respectively which were within the prescribed limits. Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of Glycosides, Carbohydrates, Steroids, Tannins and Terpenoids in both the extracts and of Alkaloids in alcoholic extract only.

CONCLUSION

Thus, all the parameters of three brands of Arogyavardhini Vati had approximately similar values having difference in the values of Alcohol soluble extractives of Brand B with the lesser value of 3.2% and of Water soluble extractives of Brand A with the lesser value of 24.0%. There was also a considerable difference in the values of Hardness and Disintegration time of Brand B with a lesser and greater values of 4.33 ± 0.763 and 65 min. respectively.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the present study on pharmaceutical, physico-chemical and phytochemical characteristics can serve as a vital source of information and provide adequate reference standards for the quality control of these formulations for future research. The quality controls are also emphasized in each lot to optimize the final product according to the Pharmacopoeial standards.

ABBREVIATIONS:

API	– Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India
IP	– Indian Pharmacopoeia
Pb	– Lead
Cd	– Cadmium

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

We declare that we have no conflict of interest.

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